

Paper 3

A STUDY ON THE PORTRAYAL OF TRANSGENDERS: A CASE STUDY ON “NAANU AVANALLA... AVALU” MOVIE

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Abstract:

Transgenders are the individuals whose gender identity differs from their biological sex. For several decades, the transgenders have been victimized to harassment, stigma, physical assault, sexual violence and are being deprived of employment and education. The current study is aimed to look into the discrimination faced by transgender character(s) in the film “Naanu Avanalla... Avalu” directed by B. S. Lingadevaru. In this study we look into the protagonist, a character named Madesha (Vidhya) who faces discrimination at various levels for being a transgender person. On the contrary, there has been significant increase in the portrayal of transgender characters in Television shows, Stand up comedies, web series and movies. Specially in a country like India, where we have a conservative society that has been treating transgenders as outcasts. Hence, we have mostly seen the negative portrayal of transgenders where we have seen them as characters who are not well adapted to the society. Only recently we have seen transgenders playing major roles in television shows and movies. The current study will also observe transgenders playing lead characters in the film “Naanu Avanalla... Avalu”.

Keywords: Transgenders, Harassment, Stigma, Physical assault, Sexual violence, Homophobia, Individual rights

I. INTRODUCTION

- *Transgenders*

According to Dietert and Dentice, “Transgender” is a broad term to describe individuals whose gender expression differs from that of the societal norms of gender that is assigned at the time of birth. The manners by which transgender individuals self-recognize and express their sexual identity fluctuate depending upon the person. Some transgender individuals display some level of manliness and/or as feminine attributes relying upon their “*gender self-identification*” (Dietert & Dentice, 2009).

- *Transgenders in India*

For centuries, transgenders have been in Indian society and several historical texts have confirmed their existence. The terms “*napumsaka*” and “*tritiyaprakriti*” have been mentioned in early Vedic literatures and Hindu mythology. In fact, Jain scriptures makes a mention of the idea of “psychological sex” that accentuated the individual’s psychological make-up that is different from their sexual character (Michelraj, 2015). A *hijra* is a person who have the attributes of both masculine and feminine genders. Ones who are born as male, went through castration (a procedure involving removal of testicles and penis), vaginoplasty, or breast implants in order to trans into a feminine identity. They are also seen wearing a feminine attire. Any individual who recognizes oneself as person of the opposite sex from their biological sex identifies oneself as a *Hijra* (Chettiar, 2015).

- *Portrayal, Negative/Positive portrayal in films*

Homophobia still being prevalent in a country like India, scholarly discussions on topics such as homosexuality is considered as a taboo by both the society and the government. However, in the recent years, discussions and depictions of homosexuality has been surfacing in the Indian cinemas and the Indian television news medium as well. Stringent rules by the Indian censor board prohibited such portrayals. Even then, some film makers used transgender portrayals in humorous manner that would sometimes end up making a mockery of the LGBTQ group by hurting their sentiments. Such portrayals are now seen shifting. Gay themed films have been surfacing and surprisingly some of them have been winning awards (Sabharwal & Sen, 2012).

- *Naanu avanalla ... avalu.. about the film, awards*

“*Naanu Avanalla..Avalu*” is a movie based on an autobiography “I am Vidya”, the real life struggles of a transgender named Living Smile Vidya. The screenplay of the movie is written by the director B S Lingadevaru (Hooli, 2016). The movie received national award for Best Actor in 62nd National Film awards (Mehta, 2015). The film also received Karnataka State award for Best actor (Male) and Best Story.

- *Why this study?*

Gender scholars have only made few mentions of the transgender portrayal in cinemas and novels. However, there must be wider focus, attention and debates on the portrayal of transgender, gender and sexuality in Indian Cinemas. Hence, this study is aimed to look into discrimination faced by transgender Character(s) in the film “*Naanu avanalla... avalu*”.

II. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

- *Qualitative analysis*

Qualitative analysis of a content emphasizes a coordinated perspective of texts and the context on which it was written. Such study goes further than merely checking words or separating objective content from writings to analyze their meanings, themes, and examples that may be evident or hidden in a specific content. This study enables researchers to comprehend social reality in subjective way but in a scientific manner (Wildemuth, 2017).

- ***Homophobia***

According to McDermott, Roen and Scourfield, 'Homophobia' is a punishment the individual gets from the society for defying the norms of a heterosexual society. This punishment can occur at various levels such as, physical, verbal abuse, rejection and isolation that eventually leads to psychological distress (McDermott, Roen, & Scourfield, 2008).

- ***Harassment***

Harassment can be defined as causing annoyance, trouble, disturbing, bothering, pestering, irritating, picking on, or molesting an individual (Elliott, 2009).

- ***Stigma***

The *hijra* (Transgenders) tends to live a double life as feminine males who have masculine appearance but have a complete feminine mental alleviation when with peers. Wearing of garments that are usually linked with females were not accepted at homes. Display of such attitudes is also not encouraged by the relatives. Exhibiting such attitudes would decrease the chances of the siblings from getting married. Some trans individuals receive familial pressure to get married and have a 'normal life' (Khan, et al., 2009).

- ***Physical assault***

Physical assault can be defined as a "law threatening act" that involves physical harm/injury to a person. This involves beating, abusing, attacking or mugging (Elliott, 2009).

- ***Sexual violence***

An act is considered as Sexual violence when it is committed on an individual who is not in a position to consent or to refuse. This could be because of a disability, abuse of authority, age or violent threats (Rutherford, Zwi, Grove, & Butchart, 2007).

- ***Education***

The trans individuals confront several challenges in pursuit of gaining proper education. These barriers include uniforms, academic records, sports and other facilities that accommodates transgendered individuals. Hence, a lot of trans individuals become victims of violence, bullying and exclusion from schools. The attitudes of the teachers and students become indicators of weather the institution is inclusive of transgenders (Byrne, 2013).

- ***Employment***

Not all organizations are inclusive of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and transgender employees. Certain individuals often do not disclose their gender identities at their workplaces. They often allow people to believe they are heterosexual. It gets difficult for transgenders, bisexuals and lesbians when the organization tolerates the homophobic attitudes of its employees. Creating inclusive workspaces and atmosphere by removing homophobic attitudes must be implemented in all work setups (Buccigrossi & Frost, 2003). The *hijras* (Transgenders) are unable to get mainstream jobs because they are less educated and the tend to exhibit a lifestyle that is unacceptable at workplaces. Which is why they are denied from getting proper jobs (Khan, et al., 2009).

- ***Individual rights/ legal protection***

Colonial era laws that criminalized the same sex behavior and gender expressions curbs down the individual rights of the individuals belonging to the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgenders (LGBT). However, recent discussions on the matter have resulted in revision of the constitutional framework to emphasis on the rights of LGBT individuals (Narain, 2018).

III. 'NAANU AVANALLA... AVALU': ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Homophobia

We can find few instances of Homophobia towards Madesha. We can observe it when Madesha is often spotted with only one friend in school. He also expresses this towards Govinda, his close friend. Madesha faces rejection from most of his classmates. Later, we also see Govinda avoiding Madesha as he comes to a realization that Madesha is falling in love with him in a way that the society does not accept. Madesha's attitude towards Govinda disturbs him and makes him uncomfortable.

Homophobia is also shown through people's reaction on seeing Vidya. At one scene we see a passenger in the train walking away after seeing Vidya approaching him.

Harassment

There are several instances in the movie where we see Madesha being harassed by the society for the way he behaved. In school, Madesha is often ridiculed by his classmates for his girlish behavior. After school, his classmates chase him in the streets making fun of him.

After Madesha grows up and continues to show feminine characteristics, his father asks him to leave the house. When Madesha moves to his sister's place, his brother in law tries to educate Madesha to behave like men. He forces him to fix his posture and body language. At one instance, Radha his sister gets annoyed while she spots Madesha watching Transgender related television program and turns of the Television by giving him a warning.

After Madesha trances into Vidya, she encounters harassment in other way. Once, a stranger at a tea stall eve teases Vidya. Though she feels uncomfortable, she tends to ignore the man. The movie also shows an instance where Vidya, Selvi and Naani are being questioned by the ticket collector in the train even after they had the reservation tickets. Vidya is also seen being mocked by passengers in train, to which Vidya responds strongly.

When Madesha returns home as Vidya, she faces rejection from father and brother in law. The brother in law rebukes Vidya for choosing a transgender lifestyle. He and Radha forces Vidya to wear a shirt and appear before her father.

Vidya also faces harassment from interviewers while she was seeking for jobs.

Stigma

Being in a Heteronormative society, Madesha is challenged psychologically. His feminine behavior attracts ridicule from his classmates. When he feels like playing Kho kho, the Physical education teacher sends him away suggesting him to play the games those linked with boys, such as Volley ball. When Madesha's father receives remarks from his friends regarding his feminine character, he gets offended by it and asks Madesha to leave the house. The Brother in law constantly asks Madesha to behave like a man. After Madesha returns home as Vidya, the father refuses to accept him as his daughter. As he worries what the society would say to Madesha's transformation. Hence, Vidya decides to leave her family.

Physical Assault

Madesha gets flogged by father for getting caught wearing his sister's clothes. Another instance of physical assault was seen after Madesha transes to Vidya where a man slaps Vidya for asking money. The same person trashes Vidya badly when she tries to protest. The film also shows the brutality of the person where he is seen repeatedly kicking Vidya. He later throws her out of the train mercilessly.

Sexual Violence

Sexual Violence in this is shown through the character Selvi who was forced into prostitution.

Education

Though Madesha had no difficulty in getting proper education, being constantly ridiculed by his classmates made him hesitant to attend classes. At one scene we could see Govinda literally dragging Madesha to college.

Employment

A couple in the train mocks at Vidya for begging. To which Vidya responds in a bold manner that she would work with dignity if she had gotten a job. There were two scenes that showed Vidya attending interviews and the interviewers rejected her the moment they got to know about her sexual identity.

Individual Rights

We see Vidya running into identity issues after going through a gender change. Her birth name Madesha becomes a hinderance in getting her a job. She tries to seek help from a lawyer to have her name changed. However, since there is no such provision for transgenders, the lawyer refused to offer her help.

IV. CONCLUSION

The movie 'Naanu Avanalla...Avalu' has both positive and negative portrayal of transgenders. However, the negative portrayal in this film was used deliberately to show the grim realities of a transgender's lifestyle. It is important to notice the lead characters of this film playing transgender roles. The movie has achieved its goal in creating awareness on including the transgenders in mainstream society and breaking the stereotype.

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